

The Effect Of Different Mouthwashes On The Force Decay of Elastomeric Chains: - An In Vitro Study

Ghazia Tarannum¹, Aftab Azam², Ragni Tandon³, Ashish Chauhan⁴

Received on: 05 July, 2024; Accepted on: 05 August 2024; Published on: 14-09-2024

¹PG Student,
Department of Orthodontics,
Saraswati Dental College
and Hospital, Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh

²Professor,
Department of Orthodontics,
Saraswati Dental College
and Hospital, Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh

³Professor & HOD,
Department of Orthodontics,
Saraswati Dental College
and Hospital, Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh

⁴Reader,
Department of Orthodontics,
Saraswati Dental College
and Hospital, Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh

Abstract

Background:Orthodontic elastomeric chains have been used by clinician for various orthodontic tooth movement and mouth rinsing is the basic step in maintaining oral hygiene. These days, a wide variety of mouthwashes are sold commercially. So, the aim of this study is to evaluate and compare the effects of three different commercially available mouthwashes on the force decay of orthodontic elastomeric chain an in vitro condition.

Method: 120 elastomeric chain sample were collected and categorized into four groups and then immersed into different mouthwashes according to their group, at different intervals of time force decay of orthodontic elastomeric chain has been evaluated with the help of digital force gauge, recorded on data sheet and statistical analysis performed.

Results:Results shows significant difference in force decay in all groups, where the maximum force decay were observed at 24hrs of interval in all groups with highest in chlorhexidine group.

Conclusion: Our study concluded that herbal mouthwashes have some beneficial effect over chlorhexidine mouthwashes during clinical practice in orthodontic tooth movement, and still further research is needed in-vivo condition.

Keywords: Orthodontic elastomeric chain, herbal, force decay, mouthwashes, chlorhexidine.

Introduction

Elastomeric power chain is regularly used in orthodontics to facilitate orthodontic tooth movement (OTM) and consolidate space.¹In Orthodontic, chains are used in many movements such as tooth derotations, incisor and canine retraction, midline correction, and traction of impacted teeth. Orthodontic elastomeric chains have many clinical advantages- they are economic, easy to use and can be adjusted to the patient's need, it does not require patient's cooperation, have good bio compatibility, are able to reduce the risk of intra oral trauma and also give strong, consistent, and mild support for the proper movements of the teeth. The force generated is irreversible, though, so eventually it will need to be replaced.²

Poor oral hygiene is a major concern during orthodontic treatment. Dentists recommend using mouth rinses during orthodontic tooth movement (OTM) to decrease caries lesions and promote oral hygiene.² It is observed that using chemical agents along with flossing and tooth brushing is better than mechanical control alone, in the way that both plaque and gingival inflammation could be decrease.³ When it comes to oral antimicrobial agents, chlorhexidine and the NaF are frequently found in mouthwash components.⁴

The mouthwashes that are sold on the market are those containing alcohol and some that do not contain alcohol. As a product that has antiseptic and anti plaque, mouthwash is always promoted to prevent plaque,

caries, gingivitis and bad breath.⁵ Numerous researches had been done in the literature to examine how various mouth rinses affect the force degradation of various traction aids.⁶

This study was carried out with the aim of evaluating and comparing the effects of three various commercially available mouth rinses which includes, chlorhexidine, chlorhexidine containing sodium fluoride, and herbal on the force decay of elastomeric chain an in-vitro condition.

Material & Methodology: This study was conducted into the Department of Orthodontics and Dento facial Orthopaedics at Saraswati Dental college, Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh. 120 elastomeric chains (continuous) of the brand Garmy were used in this study. Finally, 4 groups of 30 elastics were obtained;

Group A; (control group); Garmy Elastomeric chain in artificial saliva.

Group B; Garmy Elastomeric chain in chlorhexidine mouth wash

Group C; Garmy Elastomeric chain in chlorhexidine containing sodium fluoride mouth wash

Group D; Garmy Elastomeric chain in herbal mouthwash

How to cite this article:Dr Ghazia Tarannum et al.:
The Effect Of Different Mouthwashes On The Force
Decay Of Elastomeric Chains: - An In Vitro Study
HTAJOCD-2024

Access this article online

Website

www.healthtalk.in

Quick Response Code

A custom-made device containing 2 rows of 30 stainless steel fixtures of 17 gauge were created. The fixtures were mounted in wooden blocks and set at a particular distance from each other, each sample elastic chain contains 4 lumens were pre-stretched 100% and then mounted on SS fixtures with the force measuring about 200-250gm which is suitable for canine retraction.

For the control group, the elastomeric chains were submerged in artificial saliva and incubated at 37°C. For the other three groups, the chains were brought out of the artificial saliva every day and for 1 min. immersed in their respective mouthwash according to group distribution at the interval of 12 hr every day.

Elastic forces were tested before the test and after one hour, 24 hours and 4th week. The forces were measured by Digital force gauge in the mentioned intervals. In each group the percentage of force decay were calculated according to the initial force. The mean and standard deviation were calculated for the groups. Kolmogorov Smirnov test was performed to determine the normality of the data for determining force decay of orthodontic elastomeric chains when submerged in various mouthwashes. To evaluate the normality of data, analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used. Tukey test was used to compare the force decay among the studied groups.

Experimental group

Custom jig

Mouthwashes used

Results

Table 1-3 in our study, demonstrate and explained that the force degradation rate of orthodontic elastomeric chain shows significant difference between the time interval of the same group.

Time Intervals	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	Minimum	Maximum
Chlorhexidine	214.4194	7.64100	1.37236	201.00	230.00
Chlorhexidine + Sodium Fluoride	216.5484	7.74097	1.39032	202.00	231.00
Herbal	214.4194	8.06546	1.44860	201.00	229.00
Artificial Saline	216.4839	9.03280	1.62234	201.00	232.00
'F' statistic	686				
df	3				
P value	562 (NS)				

Table 1: Comparative evaluation of force degradation of elastomeric chains at initial time interval

Time Intervals	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	Minimum	Maximum
Chlorhexidine	80.0968	4.10167	.73668	74.00	87.00
Chlorhexidine + Sodium Fluoride	92.5806	3.68578	.66198	86.00	100.00
Herbal	100.5161	3.75829	.67501	93.00	109.00
Artificial Saline	101.6774	3.97817	.71450	94.00	110.00
'F' statistic	202.971				
Df	3				
P value	.000*				

Table 2: Comparative evaluation of force decay of elastomeric chains at 24 hours

Time Intervals	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	Minimum	Maximum
Chlorhexidine	43.9677	2.71396	.48744	39.00	50.00
Chlorhexidine + Sodium Fluoride	54.9677	2.56234	.46021	51.00	60.00
Herbal	66.6129	3.70295	.66507	59.00	73.00
Artificial Saline	76.3226	3.63673	.65318	69.00	85.00
'F' statistic	598.364				
Df	3				
P value	.000*				

Table 3: Comparative evaluation of force decay of elastomeric chains at 4 weeks

NS : Non-Significant; * - Significant

Discussion

This study was conducted into the Department of Orthodontics and Dento facial Orthopaedics at Saraswati Dental College, Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh. To assess and compare the force degradation of orthodontic elastomeric chain while using commercially available herbal and non-herbal mouthwashes and their comparison with a control group.

Orthodontic chains are essential sources of force transfer to the tooth and are used for various purposes in OTM including midline correction, impacted tooth movement and space closure(Dadgar S et al, 2020).⁷ A characteristic of orthodontic elastomeric chains is the inefficacy to deliver a continuous force level over an extended period of time. (Baty et al, 1994).⁸

Several studies however show slightly controversial force degradation results when comparing with non-latex and latex elastomers. Other key factors that can influence force degradation include temperature changes, saliva, pH, microbial and enzymatic events, chemical plaque control, as well as the duration of the extension. Mechanical degradation is deemed to be one of the ground reason behind force decayed in clinical practice.⁹

In our study, artificial saliva as Group A, indicates and provides us a related study results compared to Abdelali HALIMI et al. (2013)¹⁰ study that artificial saliva has a significant force degradation rate in the elastomeric chain. As mentioned earlier Group B were the elastomeric chain samples which immersed in chlorhexidine mouthwashes. These chains showed the greatest forced decay at the initial phase and the least was noted in 4th week. Related results were obtained in the

study guided by Sufarnap et al. (2021)¹¹ in which they had taken 150 samples of orthodontic chain and divided into 3 groups; measurements of force decay were performed with digital force gauge at various intervals. Their results show that chlor hexidine mouthwash group, has the greatest force decay comparing other groups.

Another most common mouthwash available are herbal mouthwashes, so in our study we include herbal mouthwash as Group D and there is statistically significant difference in force degradation of elastomeric chain. Similar results were obtained in a study guided by Mirhashemi et al (2021)¹² in which they classified their samples into six groups; one was the control group, and the others were exposed to different mouth rinses (including herbal) two times a day for 1 minute. At the conclusion of their study, the herbal group exhibited the acceptable force degradation.

The required amount force for orthodontic tooth movement of canine is 100-300 g. (Omid khoda, et al. July 2015).¹³ The lengths of extensions of samples were chosen so as to produce a force within the physiological limit (200 ± 5) gm as was suggested by Bousquet et al in a study of Vivek Mahajan et al (2014)¹⁴. With reference to this studies and various reviews we include 200 gm of initial force for all the samples with a SD and then classified into 4 groups, when we compare and evaluate the force decay of chains at initial time interval and also their pair wise comparison shows that there were no significant difference between all 4 groups (Table 1).

According to Table 2 which described an average loss of 50-65% of force degradation in all four groups of study during first 24hrs and the highest force decayed was observed in Group with chloro hexidine mouth rinses followed by chlor hexidine containing sodium fluoride mouthwashes while the herbal and artificial salivary group show lower impact on the force decayed as compared to above 2 groups and shows significantly effective.

As there are not many studies present regarding comparing all three mouth rinses effect on force decay of chains, Omid khoda et al. (2015)¹³ conducted a study to evaluate the effects of 3 different mouth rinses on the force decay of orthodontic chains. Chains with 2 different configurations were distributed into 8 groups. Their results indicate mouthwashes showed statistically significant differences at all points of time. They state that within the limitations, persica is preferred over chlor hexidine for oral health control during the OTM.

Comparable results we received in our study according to the Table 3, after the 4th week of time interval the force decay into the chain was approximately 65-80% distinguish with different type of mouth rinses used, where herbal mouthwashes shows the less amount of force degradation and Chlor hexidine mouthwashes results in the highest force decay rate, followed by chlor hexidine containing sodium fluoride mouthwash and artificial saliva shows the least.

To maintain an oral hygiene and to controlled the bacterial growth & plaque accumulation while an orthodontic treatment phase the patient must use mouth rinses for preserving the soft and hard tissue structure of oral cavity. By taking this into consideration, the Orthodontist should prescribe an effective component of mouthwashes to different patients, according to their Oral Hygiene Index needs during their clinical practices.

Limitations of our study were due to an in vitro setup. It has

been reported that several factors including diet, microbial flora, and functional forces could influence the force of orthodontic elastomeric chains in vivo.

Conclusion

Mouth washes are an essential component to maintain an oral hygiene for every person irrespective of going orthodontic treatment or not. Our study concluded that:

- Chlor hexidine mouth rinses showed the greatest force decayed of elastomeric chain at after 24hrs.
- Chlor hexidine containing sodium fluoride mouthwash results in a better way which reduces the amount of force decay as compared to chlor hexidine mouthwashes
- Herbal mouth washes which helps in maintaining oral hygiene, which included in our study and appeared to be the best regarding the force decay of chain.

Further studies with longer clinical observation and in-vivo studies are needed to standardize the force degradation rate of elastomeric chain by different mouthwashes available in commercial market and which prescribed by an orthodontist to maintain oral hygiene during Orthodontic treatment for the betterment of patients.

References

1. Lalitha Ch Et Al. The Effects of Varying Alcohol Concentrations Commonly Found In Mouth Rinses On The Force Decay Of Elastomeric Chain (In Vitro Study). *Journal Of Medical and Dental Science Research* 2023; Volume 10(7): 51-59.
2. Buchmann N, Senn C, Ball J, Brauchli L. Influence of initial strain on the force decay of currently available elastic chains over time. *The Angle Orthodontist*. 2012 May 1; 82(3): 529-35.
3. Sadeghian S, Heydari G, Shirvani A, Sadeghian R. The effect of sodium fluoride and listerine mouth washes on the force decay of orthodontic elastomeric chains. *J Res Med Dent Sci*. 2017; 5(5): 115-22.
4. Von Fraunhofer J A, Coffelt M P, Orbell G M. The effects of artificial saliva and topical fluoride treatments on the degradation of the elastic properties of orthodontic chains. *The Angle Orthodontist*. 1992 Dec 1; 62(4) : 265-74.
5. Bratu D C, Pop S I, Balan R, Dulescu M, Petrescu H P, Popa G. Effect of different artificial saliva on the mechanical properties of orthodontic elastomers ligatures. *Materiale Plactice*. 2013 Mar 1; 50(1): 49-52
6. Ramazanzadeh B A, Jahanbin A, Hasanzadeh N, Eslami N. Effect of sodium fluoride mouth rinse on elastic properties of elastomeric chains. *Journal of Clinical Pediatric Dentistry*. 2009 Dec 1; 34(2): 189-92.
7. Dadgar S et al. Effects of 6 different chemical treatments on force kinetics of memory elastic chains versus conventional chains: An in vitro study. *International Orthodontics*. 2020 Jun 1; 18(2): 349-58.
8. Baty D L, Storie D J, von Fraunhofer JA. Synthetic elastomeric chains: a literature review. *American Journal of Orthodontics and Dentofacial Orthopedics*. 1994 Jun 1; 105(6): 536-42.
9. Csekő K, Maróti P, Helyes Z, Told R, Riegler F, Szalma J, Gurdán Z. The effect of extrinsic factors on the mechanical behavior and structure of elastic dental ligatures and chains. *Polymers*. 2021 Dec 23; 14(1): 38.
10. Halimi A et al. Elastomeric chain force decay in artificial saliva: an in vitro study. *International Orthodontics*. 2013 Mar 1; 11(1): 60-70.
11. Sufarnap E, Harahap K I, Terry T. Effect of sodium fluoride in chlor hexidine mouthwashes on force decay and permanent deformation of orthodontic elastomeric chain. *Padjadjaran Journal of Dentistry*. 2021 Mar 31; 33(1): 74-80.
12. Mirhashemi A H, Shahroudi A S, Shahpoorzadeh K, Khameneh N H. Comparative evaluation of force decay pattern in orthodontic active tie backs exposed to five different mouth rinses: An in vitro Study. *Journal of Dental Research, Dental Clinics, Dental Prospects*. 2021; 14(4): 244.
13. Omid khoda M, Rashed R, Khodarahmi N. Evaluation of the effects of three different mouth washes on the force decay of orthodontic chains. *Dental Research Journal*. 2015 Jul; 12(4): 348.
14. Mahajan V, Singla A, Negi A, Jaj H S, Bhandari V. Influence of alcohol and alcohol free mouth rinses on force degradation of different types of space closure auxiliaries used in sliding mechanics. *Journal of Indian Orthodontic Society*. 2014 Oct; 48(4): 546-51.